

Principle and Methodology of Scientific Conservation and Preservation for Built Cultural Heritage

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Abstract

India is one of the most ancient civilizations of the world and is famous for its rich cultural heritage ranging over several millennia. The ravages of time and various weathering agencies through physico-chemical processes have been responsible for deterioration of this built cultural heritage. Moreover, human vandalism and constant changes in environmental scenarios in and around monuments added new challenges in the field of conservation. This, paper reports the principles and brief methodology of scientific conservation and preservation of different types of stone monuments in general & marbles in particular of our built cultural heritage.

Key Words: Scientific conservation, Preservation, Cultural Heritage

Introduction

India is one of the most ancient civilizations of the world and is famous for its rich cultural heritage ranging over several millennia. All these heritage buildings are located through the length and breadth of the country representing social, religious and cultural developments during the different periods of history. These cultural exhibits are built by different building materials and are of specific structural designs. These monuments are also exposed to varied climatic conditions. Growing air pollution in urban and industrial areas is a hazard not only to human beings but also to building materials of the monuments. The nature and behavior of component materials depends on the magnitude of the problem. The ravages of time and various weathering agencies through physico-chemical processes have been responsible for deterioration of our built cultural heritage. Moreover, human vandalism and constant changes in environmental scenarios in and around monuments added new challenges in the field of conservation. Many of our important monuments are also places of worship and hence these living monuments also pose more challenges in conservation. To fully understand the causes of deterioration, we have to identify different problems which act simultaneously over the monuments. Hence the causes of deterioration are complex in nature and also challenging. In a nutshell, both intrinsic and extrinsic factors are responsible for deterioration of our built cultural heritage.

Ethics of Conservation

- The objective of conservation is to prolong the life of cultural property and, if possible, to clarify the artistic and historical message therein without the loss of authenticity.
- Conservation is a cultural, artistic and craft activity, supported by scientific investigations.
- The Conservator should have a flexible pragmatic approach based on cultural consciousness, proper training, sound judgment and a sense of proportion with an understanding of community needs.
- Conservation refers to the process of documentation, analysis, cleaning, stabilization and preservation.

Conservation is Classified as

- Preventive Conservation
- Curative Conservation

Preventive Conservation

- Prevention is better than cure. Care should be taken to prevent decay or damage by indirect action
- Prevent decay by daily care, strategy before curative conservation which involves major intervention.
- A strategy to eliminate emergencies as far as possible.
- Minimum intervention at one time.
- Less expensive.
- Inspection at regular intervals.
- The intervals required depend on climate, building materials used and its environment.

Curative Conservation

- Conservation carries major intervention
- Emergent restoration
- More expensive
- Conservation beyond preventive measures
- Depends on structure / object

Investigations/Inspections

- Deterioration of monument/object classified as
 - Intrinsic factor
 - Extrinsic factor
- Intrinsic factor
 - Due to inherent quality of building materials
 - Weakness in the structure/object
- Extrinsic factor
 - Natural agents
 - Artificial agents caused by man

Factors influence the rate of alternation of stone of a monument/object

- Initial freshness of stone, its texture, its cut, its orientation in the structure, its physico mechanical characteristics.
- Nature/type of stone
- Porosity of stone
- Migration and crystallization of soluble salt
- Building designs and functional environment
- Foreign materials within the structure
- Vegetational growth, moss and lichen etc
- Climate/microclimate and environment
- Light
- Temperature and Humidity
- Insects and micro-organism
- Dust and other atmospheric pollutants

Scientific conservation and preservation of Archaeological Monuments is the responsibility of a conservator which involves as follows:

- Conservation treatment and preservation of archaeological monuments including world heritage sites
- Conservation treatment of museum exhibits and excavated objects.
- Scientific and technical studies as well as research on material heritage of different building materials, to study the causes of deterioration with a view to evolve appropriate conservation measures, in order to improve the state of preservation of our built cultural heritage and physical heritage as well.

Conservation Approach

The systematic approach to formulate the Conservation Strategies for Stone Conservation is based on diagnosis and prognosis which mainly involves following steps:

- Identification of causes for the deterioration of monuments.
- Collection of precise information about the past and present status of the monument.
- The practice of conservation, in modern age, is thus both “ Critical – historical judgement”, which is reflected in the choice of most suitable methods and conservation techniques and “ Scientific – technical knowledge”, which is the direct result of laboratory analysis
- Each conservation approach must take into account the prevailing site experience
- No single practical conservation approach can ever cover all the eventualities
- Each case will have to be assessed on its own merits

Conservation Methodology

- STRUCTURAL CONSERVATION
- SCIENTIFIC CONSERVATION
- Documentation of before, during and after stages of conservation of monuments has to be undertaken

Structural Conservation:

This involves the following steps :

- Resetting of old stones
- Renewing the missing and worn out stones
- Replacing only the deteriorated portion of stone while retaining its architectural originality
- Replacing rusted iron dowels by stainless steel dowels
- Grouting, Pinning and pointing

Scientific Conservation

Generally scientific conservation is a follow-up of structural conservation. It consists of the following steps.

- Chemical cleaning
- Use of stone strengthener
- Desalination
- Biocidal treatment of cleaned surface
- Application of preservative

Chemical Cleaning

Application of 2-3 % of Ammonia solution and 2-3% Non-ionic detergent solution, followed by gentle brushing helps in removal of micro-vegetation from the stone surface. Ammonia solution neutralizes the acids secreted by the roots of vegetational growth. Non-ionic detergent removes dust, dirt and other accretions without leaving behind any extra ions on the stone surface.

In case of lime to be removed from the stone surface- 2-3% acetic acid is used in place of ammonia.

Wash thoroughly with plain water to remove traces of chemicals left behind, if any

Precautions

- Chemical cleaning should not be drastic leading to losses of materials from the stone itself
- The cleaning process must not produce materials (soluble salts) which may cause further deterioration to stone
- The joints of stone blocks, in case of ashlar masonry, should not be abraded
- In case of marble surface, the cleaned surface must be as far as possible smooth with original surface unaffected

Observations

The behavior of micro-vegetation is significantly influenced by sulphate and nitrate ions, gaseous pollutants especially SO₂, NO₂ and in polluted environments the synergic effect is complex.

High level of particulate matter contaminated with soluble salts may favour the growth of vegetation whereas the gaseous pollutants make it dormant or may even cause death.

Desalination

- Desalination means to extract the soluble salts from the pores of the stones using paper pulp with deionized water
- The process is repeatedly carried out till the chloride test of the solution obtained by extracting the salt from paper pulp with deionized water is negative
- Cent per cent removal of salts from the pores of the stones is not possible
- The process is effective particularly for sea shore monuments

Use of stone strengthener

Chemical used – Wacker stone strengthener OH 100 based on ethyl silicate

It penetrates through capillaries deep into construction material

Ethyl silicate reacts with water from atmosphere and forms a glass like silica gel binder (SiO_2aq)

Ethanol as by-product evaporates

Final hardness reached after two weeks

Features

- Easy to apply, one pack system
- Its low molecular weight ensures optimum penetration
- It dries to form tack-free film
- No by-product that damages building material
- It forms a mineral binder that is compatible with structure
- Binder is acid resistant, therefore, resists rain water
- Does not seal pores. Construction material remain permeable to water vapour

Fungicidal Treatment

- Chemical used – 1-2% Sodium pentachlorophenate / Zinc silicofluoride in water
- It arrests vegetational growth

Sodium Pentachlorophenate is more advantageous because

- It is better soluble in water
- Zinc silicofluoride may fill / block the pores
- Zinc silicofluoride appears to cause unattractive patchy or streaky grey patch accompanied by pitting and flaking

Application of Preservative Coat

A Good preservative should have

- Good penetration depth
- No incrustation but formation of even consolidation
- No formation of salt as by-product
- No colour change and shiny surface of stone
- Permit water vapour permeability
- Reduction of absorbency of water
- Reasonable life period

Preservative in use – Wacker BS 290 dilutable with Mineral Turpentine oil in the ratio 1 : 9 - 1:18 or SMK 1311 in water single or double coat depending on the porosity of stone.

History of Preservative coating

- 1-2% PVA (Polyvinyl acetate) in toulene in single and double coat
- 1-2% PMMA (Polymethyl methacrylate) in toulene in single or double coat
- 1:30 Repellin super (Potassium Methyl silicate) and distilled water
- 1:30 Repellin super followed by 1% PMMA in toulene
- SMK 1311 in water
- Wacker BS 290 (Solvent free silicon concentrate based on silane/siloxane) and MTO (1:9 – 1:18)

Characteristics of Preservative

- Solvent free silicone concentrate based on Silane / Siloxane
- Diluted Wacker BS 290 serves as a high quality water repellent

Features

- Good penetration capacity
- High alkaline resistant
- Tack-free drying
- Effective even on damp surface
- Water repellency develops first
- Reacts with moisture first generates active ingredient and liberate alcohol
- Suitable for concrete, plasters, cement fibre boards, Sand-lime brick work and stones (Except Marble)

Protecting Facades with Silicones

Unlike film-forming coatings based on acrylic, polyurethane or epoxy resins, organo silicon water repellents do not seal the pores, but simply form a very layer on the pore walls.

A mineral surface with (a) a hydrophobic impregnation (b) filled pores (c) A sealant

Pores which have been siliconized and therefore hydrophobic can no longer be wetted by water.

The degree of wetting can be determined quantitatively as the contact angle

Wetting of a hydrophilic porous surface

Water repellency of a hydrophobic porous surface

Water vapour can diffuse

Since, the pores in hydrophobically treated masonry remain open, the building material retains its water vapour permeability or “breathability” which is one of the main criteria for successful treatment

Water under pressure is a problem

It is of course obvious that water-repellent treatment cannot render a building material resistant to ground water or driving rain, since pores in the masonry are open. The larger the pores, the greater is the problem. However, the properly applied water repellents are perfectly sufficient to render many standard building materials. The water repellent should have maximum penetration into pores and then only the efficacy of hydrophobic impregnation be guaranteed for many years or even decades.

Hydrophobic zone and water beading effect

Restoration

The object of restoration is to bring an ancient building back to its original condition in appearance by faithfully and minutely reproducing all that has been lost or destroyed by making the new work and material compatible with the structure as far as possible. In the past, restoration theories have often emphasized specific types of treatment but in India the conservation of cultural heritage is not viewed simply as a series of recipes. Consequently, specific protection and conservation strategies are likely to vary considerably according to the context and values associated with each monument or site. Nevertheless, general principles of good conservation practice do serve as a foundation for the identification and protection of heritage resources.

The Essence of Marshall's Views

- Hypothetical restorations are unwarranted, unless they are essential for the stability of a building.
- Every original member of a building should be preserved intact and dismantling and reconstruction should be undertaken only if a structure cannot be otherwise maintained.
- Restoration of carved stone, carved wood or plaster moulding should be undertaken only if Artisans are able to attain the excellence of old and in no case should mythological or other scenes be recarved.
- The essence of Marshall's views about the aim of conservation is not to reproduce what has been defaced or destroyed, but to save what is left from further injury or decay and to preserve it as a national heirloom.

Clay Pack Treatment (Specially for Marble)

- Marble stone is first cleaned with water having small quantities of Ammonia and Non-ionic detergent with mild brushing
- A 2mm thick layer of mixture of Bentonite clay / Fuller's earth (100gms), 2ml Ammonia, 1ml Non-ionic detergent, 1ml H₂O₂, 2gms Na₂CO₃, 2gms NaHCO₃ and 2 drops of Triethanolamine is applied over the stone surface
- The consistency should be controlled to prevent its flow on the surface
- Cover it with Polythene sheet for at least 2 days
- The additive influences the thixotropic characteristic of clay pack to help the complete removal of greasy accretions, trapped gaseous pollutants etc.
- The Polythene sheet is removed and the clay pack is allowed to dry and then removed, wash with water and if required by Ammonia and Non-ionic detergent
- Repeat the same procedure, if required
- The treatment is non-abrasive, non-corrosive as well as quite effective

Polishing Marble for surface protection

- The application of preservative is not effective over marble surface
- The marble surface is polished with moss agate stone using lead oxide – tin oxide(1%each) with 1% solution of Oxalic acid as a polishing medium.
- The composite polishing method has advantage over other methods using abrasive or application of wax material.

- The polished surface having in-filled oxalate film and uniform smooth surface act as a protective layer
- Particulate matter and water have least sticking affinity on the polished surface, thereby inhibiting epilithic action

Vishwanath temple, Khajuraho - A World Heritage Monument

Before conservation treatment

After conservation treatment

Cleaning of microbiological growth is important to improve the aesthetics as well as for effective preservation of the monument

Mahakal temple, Bijolia, Distt. Bhilwada, Rajasthan

Before conservation treatment

After conservation treatment

Lotus temple, Hampi – A World Heritage Monument

Before conservation treatment

After conservation treatment

**Consolidation of basalt rock sculpture using Wacker OH –
100CaveNo.19AjantaCaves – A World Heritage Monument**

Yakshni's figure before and after restoration work

Brass Statue Consolidated by Epoxy Resin + Filler (Different Stages of Conservation)

Before conservation treatment

After conservation treatment

Taj Mahal, Agra – A World Heritage Monument

Before conservation treatment

After conservation treatment

Hoshang Shah's Tomb, Mandu

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